

Entrepreneurial Environment And COVID-19: An In-Depth Bibliometric Analysis Of The Research Field

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Abstract: *In the current inquiry, the author starts from the idea that, when humanity is hit by a crisis similar to the health crisis caused by the spread of the SARSCoV2 virus, the business environment undergoes dramatic changes. The implications of these changes are structural, profound, as it is generally recognized that entrepreneurship is a powerful trigger for the growth and economic development of all communities and societies. The main objective of this paper is to identify the interest in the field of scientific research on the issue of entrepreneurship, in the complicated situation generated by the health crisis. Using as research methodology the in-depth bibliometric analysis, the author establishes the inventory and the performance of the publishing activity in the previously mentioned field. In this regard, on February 4, 2022, the Web of Science database was queried. This includes documents such as: articles, editorial materials, proceeding papers, review articles, data papers, etc. The query by the topic "entrepreneurship" and "COVID-19" provided 413 scientific papers for which the two concepts are found at least simultaneously in the title, abstract or keywords. The research results reflect the increased interest in the research topic specified above, in the sense that in the two years in which the database was created, it highlighted a significant number of documents.*

Keywords: *bibliometric analysis, COVID-19, crisis, entrepreneurship, keyword analysis, research field map, scientific document*

I. INTRODUCTION

The early 2020s find all of humanity in a deep health crisis caused by the rapid spread of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19). Although the World Health Organization initially declared the disease a state of emergency, on January 30, 2020, just before the end of March, the situation was described as a pandemic, as it affected most parts of the globe to varying degrees. North America and Europe are the most affected continents in this regard (Hall et al., 2020; Cankurtaran et al., 2020). This situation is identified as the second global shock of the turn of the century, after the Great Recession of 2008, a "black swan" event that will fundamentally change the way business is done and "life as we knew it" (Bosma et al., 2021).

Health thus becomes the most important concern. From the first moments of the outbreak of the health crisis, a harsh series of measures were adopted such as: quarantine, extended restrictions on mobility and travel, interruption of activities that were not considered essential, cancellation of events with more than ten participants. These actions have far-reaching negative economic effects.

Threats to the economies of the world will be accounted for by: declining GDP, rising unemployment, diminishing access to education, closing down businesses, changing the coordinates of the energy system, accentuating social inequalities, increasing the risks of health workers (Mofijur et al., 2021, Ratten, 2021). The balance of millions of individuals and companies is subject to increased uncertainty.

As a rule, periods of crisis have a stronger influence on the microenterprise and SME sectors than on large firms (Juergensen et al., 2020; Reiner et al., 2020). The inventory of specialized literature highlights the two facets of the change in the ecosystem of SMEs, as a result of going through the crisis.

- a) On the one hand, the number of entrepreneurial businesses is declining. Given their limited resources - financial, human and technical, they become more vulnerable to internal and external events, which means that a return to equilibrium and growth after a crisis takes longer (Juergensen et al., 2020, Laufs & Schwens, 2014). This vulnerability became apparent during the Great Recession of 2008, when SMEs experienced both a sharp drop in demand and a severe financial decline. The decline in demand has mainly affected manufacturing SMEs (Juergensen et al., 2020). Thus, as a result of the health crisis, the entrepreneurial sector follows the formula presented above. It faces a heavy economic burden, as customers significantly reduce or even completely stop spending, financiers are becoming more and more careful about their investments (Eggers, 2020), and supply chains and business relationships are becoming increasingly vulnerable (Caballero-Morales, 2021). Therefore, liquidity flows become insufficient compared to payments related to salaries and rents or to possible investments in own infrastructure.
- b) On the other hand, due to their small size and much more flexible hierarchical structure, SMEs are more flexible, easier to adapt (Juergensen et al., 2020). If they have significant knowledge about the sector in which they operate and know how to exploit market opportunities, they become more efficient, they register economic growth (Devece et al., 2016). In addition, companies with "entrepreneurial orientation" ensure capabilities such as proactivity, innovation and willingness to take risks (Eggers, 2020, Shaker, 2021).

In order to counteract the phenomena presented in point a), decision-makers around the world are committed to implementing public policies that support and stimulate the business environment, facilitating regional competitiveness and even economic growth (Ratten, 2021). Protecting jobs is also becoming a major concern for the governments of the world's states. Public loan and subsidy schemes are designed and granted to help SMEs survive in the new economic crisis that has come along with the health crisis. Moreover, to sustain public health, the entrepreneurial ecosystem has been harnessed by public authorities by building public-private partnerships (Ratten, 2021).

Also, in this context, the academic community can formulate proposals for solutions through which the entrepreneurial ecosystem can remake its business models, so that companies can demonstrate their efficiency in different markets, under different constraints and restrictions

(Caballero-Morales, 2021). Thus, the literature proposes methodologies for streamlining the SME sector in two directions: to optimize processes and reduce the costs and waste of SMEs and to innovate to generate significant results in the future (Nah & Siau, 2020, Caballero-Morales, 2021).

In the context of the crisis, innovation is considered a significant and defining condition on which the organizational resilience of SMEs belonging to all sectors of activity depends (Nah & Siau, 2020, Caballero-Morales, 2021). The firm's propensity to innovate is determined, according to Carland et al. (1984), Rajapathirana & Hui (2018), Martin (2016), as the ability to:

1. create new economic goods or improve existing ones to meet current market needs;
2. adopt new products to anticipate future needs;
3. develop and apply new or improved processing technologies and processes, as compared to the stage known until then, at least for the sector in which they are applied;
4. the purchase of new raw materials or semi-finished products;
5. make a significant change in the organization of processes, based less on technology and more on management methods and techniques in an organization or in the sector in which it operates;
6. take advantage of market opportunities, through significant changes in design or packaging, in the placement, promotion and pricing of a product, accepted by the market.

Taking into account these realities, as well as the large number of scientific papers belonging to the scientific literature in the field, five research questions arise:

- How did the interest in the research area on the issue of entrepreneurship in a pandemic context evolve?
- Who are the most prolific authors of entrepreneurial literature during COVID-19?
- Which scientific publications have the highest number of research papers on the topic? What about the most citations?
- Which countries / regions contribute to the development of research activity on the issue of entrepreneurship in a pandemic context?
- What are the key words around which specialized literature on entrepreneurship revolves in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic?

As such, so as to answer these questions we used the quantitative bibliometric analysis of the Web of Science Core Collection database, for the period 2020-2022.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Objectives

The objective of the research is to identify the scientific interest for the issue of entrepreneurship in the complicated context of the health crisis generated by the SARSCoV2 virus.

B. Research Methodology

In order to explore the topic, an in-depth inventory of the flow of literature is made, which shows concern for the

various aspects of entrepreneurial behavior in the new pandemic conditions, through bibliometric analysis. The investigation aims to identify the current stage and dynamics of scientific research. The choice of this type of analysis is supported, first of all, by its very purpose, that of studying the concept and not the document, publication or author (Pivovar-Sulej et al., 2021). The information provided by the query of the most used database by researchers - Web of Science (Xu et al., 2021) was used.

The steps taken in carrying out the bibliometric analysis are described in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Stages of bibliometric analysis

Source: After Janik et al. (2021)

Examining the Web of Science Core Collection database generated an impressive number of documents, given the short period of time that conditions the search - February 2020 / January 2022. Accessing it on February 4, 2022, generated a number of 413 documents for which the topic "Entrepreneurship" AND "COVID-19" was found at least in the title, abstract or in the keywords. According to the type of texts, they are grouped in 362 articles - of which 66 early access, 19 editorial materials, 18 proceedings papers, 13 review articles and one data paper. The author of this article appreciated that it is not necessary to refine the search by introducing additional filters.

Given the time of querying the Web of Science database, no bibliometric analysis similar to the one present in this database was identified.

Conducting analysis of the flow of literature on various forms of entrepreneurship in the context of the health crisis, required the use of the VOSviewer software tool (version 1.6.18) developed by researchers Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Watman from Leiden University. This product mediates, by making maps, the graphical representation of the links

between the keywords / that appear most frequently in the investigated document base.

the countries that contribute to the research activity, while Table 1 highlights the languages used for this purpose.

III. THE RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS

In order to establish the relevant features of the published literature, the following bibliometric indicators will be examined: the research fields with the highest number of published papers, the languages used for publishing the papers, the geographical areas that generate the most writings, the publications with the highest number of research papers, total number of citations per document, average number of citations per document, top ten relevant authors on the topic, H-index, keywords and review of the most important research articles.

The WoS Core Collection database query found that the 413 documents addressing the pandemic entrepreneurship issue were included in 67 Web Of Science Categories. Figure 2 distributes the published documents according to this

Table 1: Distribution of scientific documents according to the languages used for publication

Languages	Record Count	% of 414
English	380	92.01
Spanish	13	3.148
Portuguese	8	1.937
Russian	8	1.937
French	3	0.726
Italian	1	0.242

Source: Own analysis of the Web of Science database

criterion.

Figure 2: The distribution of documents by research fields

Source: Own analysis of the Web of Science database

The main research directions are Business and Management. These two include 244 documents, representing 60% of the documents included in the database. Approx. 15% of the documents belong to the Economics field, representing the third category in order of importance. Unsurprisingly, other significant areas covering the research issue are: Green Sustainable Science Technology (44 papers, representing 10.65%), Environmental Sciences and Studies (85 papers, representing 20.58%) Psychology Multidisciplinary (19 papers, 4.6%) and Hospitality Leisure Sport Tourism (10 documents, representing 2.42%). Moreover, these Web of Science Categories can be corroborated with the spheres of activity belonging to the real economy that were most strongly influenced by the pandemic situation.

The vast majority of scientific papers that included the terms “entrepreneurship” and “COVID-19” at least in title, abstract, or keywords were developed in 2021 (73.6%), showing an intensification of interest in the issue of the subject of this article.

Figure 3 highlights the frontiers of research on entrepreneurial behavior during the pandemic, depending on

Figure 3: Distribution of documents according to the countries that contribute to the research activity

Source: Own analysis of the Web of Science database

The WoS database assigns the 413 research papers to 85 countries. According to the data collected (Figure 3), the top five countries with the largest contribution to the development of the issue, cumulating 52.8% of the writings, are the USA, England, Australia, Spain and Italy. Also, in the two years under analysis, Peoples R China and Germany each generate over 20 works. The native country of the author of this article, Romania, occupies a prestigious 12th place, preceded by Poland (14 documents, 3.39%).

As one could easily anticipate, English is the most widely used language in the writing of works belonging to the database (380 documents, representing 92% of the total). At least two arguments determine these statistical values: (a) high-impact academic journals are in English and (b) the vast majority of researchers know this language (Rey-Marti et al., 2016). According to Table 1, in second place, but at a great distance, is the Spanish language (13 writings, 3%).

Table 2 provides information on the top 10 scientific publications with the highest number of papers, while

highlighting the average number of citations per publication, the H index, and the JIF Scientometric Index calculated by Journal

Citation Reports 2020.

Publication Title	Journal Impact Factor - 2020 (JIF)	Record Count	% of 413	Citations average per item	H-Index
Sustainability	3.251	39	9.443	3	5
Small Business Economics	8.164	12	2.906	3.75	3
Frontiers in Psychology	2.988	9	2.179	2.22	2
Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies	-	8	1.937	8.5	4
Journal of Enterprising Communities People and Places in the Global Economy	-	7	1.695	7.86	3
International Small Business Journal Researching Entrepreneurship	5.473	6	1.453	15.83	5
Journal of Business Research	7.55	6	1.453	24.67	2
International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior Research	4.412	5	1.211	7.4	1
International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship	-	5	1.211	1	2
Journal of Asian Finance Economics and Business	-	5	1.211	1.2	2

Table 2: Top 10 scientific papers in scientific journals

Source: Own analysis of the Web of Science database

The top five journals reviewed by researchers, based on the number of papers published, are: Sustainability (39 papers), Small Business Economics (12 papers), Frontiers in Psychology (9 papers), Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies (8 papers) and Journal of Enterprising Communities People and Places in the Global Economy (7 documents). However, the order of the first five journals changes substantially when considering the criterion of the average number of citations, which shows the increased interest of researchers in citing articles published in journals with significant JIF. Showing the popularity and recognition of journals, this top is as follows: Journal of Business Research (JIF 7.55, average per item 24.67), International Small Business Journal Researching Entrepreneurship (JIF 5.473, average per item 15.83), Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies (average per item 8.5), Journal of Enterprising Communities People and Places in the Global Economy (average per item per item 7.86) and International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior Research (JIF 4.412, average per item 7.4).

The minimum number of citations of a journal as well as the correlations created are reflected by the map in Figure 4, generated by the VOSviewer software. Minimum number of citations of a source was 5. Out of 1234 sources generated, only 77 meet the threshold (6.24%).

The distance between the two journals indicates the connection between them from the point of view of co-citation. The shorter the distance between them, the stronger their relationship.

The top five journals that record the most comprehensive total link are: Journal of Business Research (Cluster 1 - red, 2170 strengths), Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice (Cluster 2 - green, 1411 strengths), Small Business Economics (Cluster 2 - green, 1303 strengths), International Entrepreneurship and Management (Cluster 3 - blue, 1168 strengths), and Journal of Business Venturing (Cluster 4 - yellow, 1148 strengths).

Next, the scientific writings are analyzed in accordance with their authors. The 413 scientific papers correspond to a number of 1145 authors. Table 3 highlights the top ten relevant authors who addressed the issue of entrepreneurship under the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The most prolific author is Vanessa Ratten, who has published 13 scientific studies, recording 214 citations (average per item 16.46). The distribution of the total number of citations is as follows: 18 citations corresponding to six publications in 2020 and 182 citations according to seven publications in 2021. For 2022 no citations are registered.

Also noteworthy are the large number of citations by researchers Robert Fairlie (3 publications, times cited 78, average per item 26) and Sascha Kraus (3 publications times cited 72, average per item 24).

Asset Dynamics (IFKAD 2020). It belongs to the authors Paunescu Carmen and McDonnell-Naughton Mary.

It is observed that the authors from the delimited network are grouped in two big categories.

By using the VOS tool, the author citation network is delimited (Figure 5). Under the conditions of restricting the minimum number of citations of an author 2 of the 1815 authors, 308 meet the threshold.

Figure 5: Map of citation links between authors

Source: Own analysis of the Web of Science database using VOSviewer

On the left side of Figure 5 are the authors who communicate and cooperate with each other, thus creating a network connection graph. The left side of the figure contains individual nodes, highlighting the authors who do not cooperate with each other.

Also, given the short period of time subject to analysis, it can be mentioned that the large share of total citations of articles belonging to the research field was recorded in 2021 - 1579 citations, 84.6%.

Using VOS, a map of the intensity of co-occurrence between author keywords is drawn up (Figure 6). Minimum number of occurrences of a keyword has been set for 1 word. Out of 151 keywords that meet the threshold, 29 were selected. The map provides the image of four clusters comprising the following keywords:

- Cluster 1 (red color) reflects keywords specific to the mode of action in the entrepreneurial ecosystem, in the conditions generated by the pandemic: collaboration, coronavirus, crisis management, entrepreneurial ecosystems, lifestyle entrepreneurship, logical service-dominant, social entrepreneurship, social policy, social value, sport entrepreneurship, sport industry, value co-creation.
- Cluster 2 (green color) reveals the importance of innovation and digitalization in the new pandemic conditions, through the following keywords: covid-19, crisis, digitalization, entrepreneurship, gender, innovation, resilience, sports entrepreneurship and theory of planned behavior.

- Cluster 3 (blue color) highlights terms specific to the manifestation and entrepreneurial behavior in the conditions of the health crisis: high-quality entrepreneurs, necessity entrepreneurship, opportunity entrepreneurship, pandemic, potential entrepreneurs, shock.
- Cluster 4 (yellow color) groups the specific terms of the educational system in pandemic conditions: education, entrepreneurship education.

Finally, it is justified to analyze the main parameters of the articles that are distinguished both according by the academic interest of entrepreneurship in the context of the health crisis generated by the SARSCoV2 virus, and according to the number of citations - total and average.

Article 1: “Employee adjustment and well-being in the era of COVID-19: Implications for human resource management”

Authors: Carnevale & Hatak

Title of scientific journal: Journal of Business Research

Year of publishing: 2020

Total / average number of citations in Web of Science:

139/ 46.33

Topic approached: The article identifies and analyzes the challenges that the COVID-19 pandemic poses to human resource management (HRM), as organizations are forced to support their employees to cope with a different and more difficult work environment. The authors identify hitherto untapped sources of social support that entrepreneurial firms

should capitalize on so that employees can adapt to their current work environment and find balance and well-being.

Title of scientific journal: Sustainable Production and Consumption

Article 2: "Impact of covid-19 on the social, economic,

environmental and energy domains: Lessons learnt from a global pandemic"

Year of publishing: 2021

Authors: Mofijur et al.

Total / average number of citations in Web of Science: 109/ 54.5

Figure 6: Map of links between keyword

Source: Own analysis of the Web of Science database using VOSviewer

Topic approached: The article proposes a comprehensive analysis of the impact that the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus has had on three interdependent levels - socio-economic life, the ecological field and the energy sector, as well as the measures applied to combat the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. In this sense, the research reviews the socio-economic impact by changing the following indicators: low GDP, high rates of poverty and unemployment, changes in education systems, increased risks of health workers and changes in the form and nature of work. The impact on the energy field is identified, first of all, by the increase of the residential energy demand as a result of the mobility restrictions, at the same time with the decrease of the industrial and commercial energy demand and by delays of the energy projects. These delays will create uncertainty even in the near future. The impact of the pandemic on the ecological field is reflected by significant reductions in environmental pollution due to the decrease of NO₂, PM and noise emissions. The article also identifies the effectiveness of the initiatives established by the authorities and companies and summarizes the lessons learned.

Topic approached: The article identifies a solution for crisis management in the hospitality industry, in order to combat the effects of the crisis generated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors specify that, until now, such solutions were

addressed only in the context of terrorism, natural disasters and financial crises. Therefore, a case study of six companies in the Austrian hospitality industry proposes a business model innovation (BMI) solution in a pandemic context. The study's findings show that if applied, BMI creates new revenue streams and provides a high level of liquidity. The implementation of BMIs involves small changes in the business model, but which can be implemented quickly. Given that the closure of the business during the pandemic has increased the time resources associated with operational activities, these resources can be directed towards the strategic development of a hospitality company. Initiated in response to a crisis, companies that take advantage of the opportunity for change may apply BMI to generate long-term positive financial effects. In particular, SMEs, which do not generally allocate capacity in strategy development, can benefit from the application of BMI as a way of responding to the crisis. Moreover, the authors appreciate that, while extended government support slows down BMI, financial constraints will cause SMEs in the hospitality industry to develop BMI.

Article 3: "The role of business model innovation in the hospitality industry during the COVID-19 crisis"

Authors: Breier et al.

Title of scientific journal: International Journal of Hospitality Management

Year of publishing: 2021

Total / average number of citations in Web of Science:

53/ 26.5

Article 4: "The impact of COVID-19 on small business owners: Evidence from the three months after widespread social-distancing restrictions"

Author: Fairlie R.

Title of scientific journal: Journal of Economics and Management Strategy

Year of publishing: 2020

Total / average number of citations in Web of Science:

64/ 21.33

Topic approached: The article analyzes the demographics of small businesses in the United States by specific indicators, such as: Number of business owners, Number of active business owners by demographic group before and after COVID - 19 (male, female, black, Latinx, Asian, white, immigrant, native), Number of active business owners by industry. Representative data from the current April Population Survey are used, the first month to highlight the early effects of pandemic closures. The processed data show that the number of active business owners decreased by 22% compared to February. Significant share of declines were recorded among minority-owned homeowners as follows: African-American business fell by 41%, Latinx by 32%, and Asian business by 26%. Also, depending on the economic branch, the most affected businesses were commercial activities. The statistical data provided in the study are important both for future public policies and for the dissemination of future economic disparities.

Article 5: “*International entrepreneurship in the post Covid world*”

Author: Shaker A. Zahra

Title of scientific journal: Journal of World Business

Year of publishing: 2021

Total / average number of citations in Web of Science:

45/ 22.5

Topic approached: The article highlights some of the changes that the pandemic period has generated on the types of international entrepreneurial activities and on the way in which they could take place in the post-pandemic period. Among the changes that took place with the COVID-19 pandemic, the study recognizes: the deterioration of international institutions that provide guidance on fair trade and dispute resolution, the structural change in global supply chains, the degradation of business networks considered fundamental to innovation, learning, access to resources, etc. The post-pandemic opportunities of the international business environment could be: intensifying online business, innovating on a global scale, changing entrepreneurial orientation, integrating social missions into the economic activity of international companies.

IV. CONCLUSIONS, STUDY LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The issue of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the entrepreneurial environment has launched a significant stream of scientific literature. The approaches regarding the correlation between entrepreneurship and COVID-19 are varied, offering many choices. We list here a number of topics, without limiting this series: the opportunities of entrepreneurship in times of crisis, the dynamics of entrepreneurial demography, the challenges of human resources policies, combating poverty and social inequalities through entrepreneurship, the transformations generated by the application of innovative processes and digitalization, public policy challenges to support entrepreneurship, the prospects of international entrepreneurship.

The present paper evaluates by bibliometric analysis (quantitative research method) descriptive and performance statistics of the main scientometric coordinates of the literature flow on the topic. Support information was obtained from the Web of Science Core Collection database query. The data was integrated and processed using the VOSviewer software tool (version 1.6.18).

Among the results obtained from the research we would like to mention:

- The 413 documents dealing with the impact of the COVID-19 health crisis on the entrepreneurial environment have been included in 67 Web of Science Categories. The five main research directions were: Business, Management, Economics, Green Sustainable Science Technology and Environmental Sciences.
- The most important countries that have contributed to the development of the field, accumulating 52.8% of the scientific papers are the USA, England, Australia, Spain and Italy. 380 documents, representing 92% of the total, were published in English.
- Depending on the average number of citations, the top five academic journals included: Journal of Business Research (JIF 7.55, average per item 24.67), International Small Business Journal Researching Entrepreneurship (JIF 5.473, average per item 15.83), Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies (average per item 8.5), Journal of Enterprising Communities People and Places in the Global Economy (average per item 7.86) and International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior Research (JIF 4.412, average per item 7.4).
- Vanessa Ratten was the most prolific author, publishing 13 scientific studies, recording 214 citations (average per item 16.46). Depending on the large number of citations, the authors of entrepreneurial literature Robert Fairlie (times cited 78, average per item 26) and Sascha Kraus (times cited 72, average per item 24) stood out.
- In 2021, 86.64% of the total number of citations was registered, while in 2020, 92 citations were registered, and in 2022, 195 citations were recorded.
- On the map related to the intensity of co-occurrence between author keywords, 29 words were selected out of 151 possible, segmented into four clusters. The most important nodes are created around the words entrepreneurship and COVID-19 (green cluster), crisis management and social entrepreneurship (red cluster).

The limits of this analysis overlap with the limits of quantitative bibliometric research. In order to have a broader perspective on the issue of entrepreneurship under the influence of the health crisis, the author of this paper proposes to correlate the impact of this topic with the impact of opportunities offered by innovation and digitalization on the business environment in the post COVID-19 period.

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